

Quantum codes obtained through (ν) -Constacyclic codes over $Z_3 + \nu Z_3$

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Abstract: In this work, structural properties of Quantum codes from Constacyclic codes over finite commutative non-chain ring $\mathfrak{R} = Z_3 + \nu Z_3$ are contemplated, where $\nu^2 = 1$ and Gray map is defined between $\mathfrak{R}$ and Z_3^2 , where Z_3 is field with 3 elements. The parameters of quantum error-correcting codes acquired by disintegrated (ν) -Constacyclic codes into two codes over Z_3 . As an application, quantum codes are cited in the paper.

2010 AMS Classification: 94B60, 94B65.

Keywords and phrases: Cyclic codes, Constacyclic codes, Finite Rings, Quantum codes.

Introduction

There has been a sea growth in the research of a quantum codes since the discovery that quantum secure quantum data is equivalent to classical code ensure classical data. Quantum codes adequately defeat decoherence. Quantum codes provide an efficient way to overcome decoherence. Firstly quantum codes were discovered by Shor [10]. Later in, a method for obtaining quantum codes through classical Codes were used by Calderbank et al. [4]. Since then there has been an tremendous growth in the theory of quantum codes and several authors constructed many better quantum codes through cyclic codes over finite field F_q (q is the power of some prime) with self orthogonal properties (for reference see [1, 5, 7]).

The construction for finding quantum codes through cyclic codes of odd length over finite chain ring $F_2 + uF_2$ where $u^2 = 0$ was first proposed by Qian et al. [9]. Inspired by this study, Kai and Zhu made development for quantum codes through cyclic codes of odd length over finite chain ring $F_4 + uF_4$ where $u^2 = 0$ in [6]. Next, Qian gave a new method to obtain quantum codes through cyclic codes over finite non-chain ring $F_2 + \nu F_2$ where $\nu^2 = \nu$ of arbitrary length in [8]. Also, Cengellenmis [3] investigated cyclic codes over the ring $F_3 + \nu F_3$ where $\nu^2 = 1$. Recently, Ashraf and Mohammad [2] defined a method to obtain quantum codes through cyclic codes over the finite non-chain ring $F_3 + \nu F_3$ where $\nu^2 = 1$. This motivates us to consider (ν) -Constacyclic codes over the finite non-chain ring $Z_3 + \nu Z_3$ where $\nu^2 = 1$ to obtain good quantum codes. The rest of the paper is arranged in the following way, Section 2 is Preliminaries in which some fundamental properties and some essential definitions have been given. Section 3 includes Gray Map from the considered ring to Z_3^2 and we presented the development of quantum codes through (ν) -constacyclic codes over the considered ring which are exemplified in section 4.

Preliminaries

Let Z_3 be a finite field with 3 elements. Now, we first start with a general overview of the ring $\mathfrak{R} = Z_3 + \nu Z_3$ having characteristic 3 with $\nu^2 = 1$, is a commutative, non-chain, semi-local finite ring with 9 elements. $1, 2, \nu, 2\nu$ are the units of the ring $\mathfrak{R}$. Ideals $\langle \nu - 1 \rangle$ and $\langle \nu + 1 \rangle$ are the only maximal ideals the ring $\mathfrak{R}$. Since it is apparent that $\mathfrak{R}/\langle \nu - 1 \rangle$, $\mathfrak{R}/\langle \nu + 1 \rangle$ both are isomorphic to Z_3 .

Now by chinese remainder theorem, the considered ring can be expressed as $\mathfrak{R} \cong \langle \nu - 1 \rangle \oplus \langle \nu + 1 \rangle \cong Z_3 \oplus Z_3$. Therefore, an arbitrary element $\alpha + \nu\beta$ of the $\mathfrak{R}$ can be uniquely expressed as $\alpha + \nu\beta = (\alpha - \beta)(\nu - 1) - (\alpha + \beta)(\nu + 1)$ for all $\alpha, \beta \in Z_3$.

A nonempty subset K of $\mathfrak{R}^n$ is a linear code over $\mathfrak{R}$ of length n . If K is an $\mathfrak{R}$ -submodule of $\mathfrak{R}^n$ and the elements of K are codewords. Let Υ, Λ and J are the maps from $\mathfrak{R}^n$ to $\mathfrak{R}^n$ defined as $\Upsilon(\chi_0, \chi_1, \dots, \chi_{n-1}) = (\chi_{n-1}, \chi_0, \dots, \chi_{n-2})$,

$\Lambda(\chi_0, \chi_1, \dots, \chi_{n-1}) = (-\chi_{n-1}, \chi_0, \dots, \chi_{n-2})$, $J(\chi_0, \chi_1, \dots, \chi_{n-1}) = ((1 - 2\nu\omega)\chi_{n-1}, \chi_0, \dots, \chi_{n-2})$,

respectively. Then K is a cyclic, negacyclic, (ν) -constacyclic if $\Upsilon(K) = K$, $\Lambda(K) = K$, $J(K) = K$ respectively. For the arbitrary elements $\chi = (\chi_0, \chi_1, \dots, \chi_{n-1})$ and

$\psi = (\psi_0, \psi_1, \dots, \psi_{n-1})$ of $\mathfrak{R}$, the inner product is defined as $\chi \cdot \psi = (\chi_0\psi_0 + \chi_1\psi_1 + \dots + \chi_{n-1}\psi_{n-1})$.

If $\chi \cdot \psi = 0$, then χ and ψ are orthogonal. If K is a linear code over $\mathfrak{R}$ of length n , then the dual code of K is defined as $K^\perp = \{ \chi \in \mathfrak{R}^n : \chi \cdot \psi = 0 \text{ for all } \psi \in K \}$.

which is also a linear code over the ring $\mathfrak{R}$ of length n . A code K is said to be self orthogonal if $K \subseteq K^\perp$ and said to be self dual if $K = K^\perp$.

The hamming weight $w_H(\chi)$ for any codeword $\chi = (\chi_0, \chi_1, \dots, \chi_{n-1}) \in \mathfrak{R}^n$ is defined as the number of all non-zero components in $\chi = (\chi_0, \chi_1, \dots, \chi_{n-1})$. The minimum weight of a code K , that is, $w_H(K)$ is the least weight among all of its non zero codewords. The Hamming distance between two codes $\chi = (\chi_0, \chi_1, \dots, \chi_{n-1})$ and $\psi = (\psi_0, \psi_1, \dots, \psi_{n-1})$ of $\mathfrak{R}^n$, denoted by $d_H(\chi, \psi) = w_H(\chi - \psi)$ and is defined as $d_H(\chi, \psi) = |\{i | \chi_i \neq \psi_i\}|$.

Minimum distance of K , denoted by d_H and is given by minimum distance between the different pairs of codewords of the linear code K . For any codeword $\chi = (\chi_0, \chi_1, \dots, \chi_{n-1}) \in \mathfrak{R}^n$, the lee weight is defined as $w_L(\chi) = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} w_L(\chi_i)$ and lee distance of $(\chi, \hat{\chi})$ is given by $d_L(\chi, \hat{\chi}) = w_L(\chi - \hat{\chi}) = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} w_L(\chi_i - \hat{\chi}_i)$.

Minimum lee distance of K is denoted by d_L and is given by minimum lee distance of different pairs of codewords of the linear code K .

Quantum Codes through (ν) -Constacyclic Codes over $\mathfrak{R}$

The Gray map φ from the ring $\mathfrak{R}$ to Z_3^2 , that is, $\varphi: \mathfrak{R} \rightarrow Z_3^2$ is defined as

$$\varphi(w = w_1 + \nu w_2) = (w_1, w_2)$$

It is obvious that, the map φ is linear and distance preserving isometry from $(\mathfrak{R}^n, d_L)$ to (Z_3^{2n}, d_H) , where d_L and d_H are the Lee distance and Hamming distance in $\mathfrak{R}^n$ and Z_3^{2n} respectively.

For a linear code K of length n over $\mathfrak{R}$, we define

$$K_1 = \{a \in Z_3^n \mid \text{for some } b \in Z_3^n \text{ such that } (a(1+\nu) + b(1-\nu)) \in K\}$$

$$K_2 = \{b \in Z_3^n \mid \text{for some } a \in Z_3^n \text{ such that } (a(1+\nu) + b(1-\nu)) \in K\}$$

be two ternary codes.

Therefore, K_1 and K_2 are the linear codes over Z_3 of length n . Moreover, the linear code K can be uniquely expressed as $K = (1+\nu)K_1 \oplus (1-\nu)K_2$ and also $|K| = |K_1| |K_2|$.

The following proposition can be obtained directly by the above defined Gray map φ .

Proposition 3.1 Let K be a linear code over the ring $\mathfrak{R}$ of length n . If K is self orthogonal, then $\varphi(K)$ is also self orthogonal.

Proof. Let K be a self orthogonal code and $\eta_1, \eta_2 \in K$ such that $\eta_1 = \xi_1 + \nu\varpi_1$ and $\eta_2 = \xi_2 + \nu\varpi_2$ where $\xi_1, \xi_2, \varpi_1, \varpi_2 \in Z_3^n$. From the definition of self orthogonality, $\eta_1 \cdot \eta_2 = 0$, that is, $\xi_1 \xi_2 + \varpi_1 \varpi_2 + \nu(\xi_1 \varpi_2 + \xi_2 \varpi_1) = 0$, it follows that $\xi_1 \xi_2 + \varpi_1 \varpi_2 = \xi_1 \varpi_2 + \xi_2 \varpi_1 = 0$. Now, applying φ on η_1, η_2 , we have $\varphi(\eta_1) = (\xi_1, \varpi_1)$ and $\varphi(\eta_2) = (\xi_2, \varpi_2)$ and hence $\varphi(\eta_1) \cdot \varphi(\eta_2) = \xi_1 \xi_2 + \xi_1 \varpi_2 + \xi_2 \varpi_1 + \varpi_1 \varpi_2 = \xi_1 \xi_2 + \varpi_1 \varpi_2 = 0$ this implies $\varphi(K)$ is self orthogonal.

Lemma 3.2 Let $K = (1+\nu)K_1 \oplus (1-\nu)K_2$ be a linear code over the ring $\mathfrak{R}$ of length n such that K_1 be $[n, k_1, d_1]$, K_2 be $[n, k_2, d_2]$ are also linear codes. Then $\varphi(K)$ is a q -ary linear code having parameters $[2n, k_1 + k_2, \min(d_1, d_2)]$.

Lemma 3.3 Let $K = (1+\nu)K_1 \oplus (1-\nu)K_2$ be a linear code over the ring $\mathfrak{R}$ of length n where K_1, K_2 are linear code over Z_3 . Then K is a (ν) -constacyclic codes over the ring $\mathfrak{R}$ of length n if and only if K_1 is Cyclic code and K_2 is negacyclic code over Z_3 of length n .

Proof. Let $\dot{a} = (\dot{a}_0, \dot{a}_1, \dots, \dot{a}_{n-1}) \in K_1$ and $\dot{b} = (\dot{b}_0, \dot{b}_1, \dots, \dot{b}_{n-1}) \in K_2$. For an arbitrary element $\zeta_i = (1+\nu)\dot{a}_i + (1-\nu)\dot{b}_i \in K$ where $\dot{a}_i, \dot{b}_i \in Z_3$ for $i = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$.

$$\text{Let } \zeta = (\zeta_0, \zeta_1, \dots, \zeta_{n-1}) \in K.$$

First we assume that K is (ν) -constacyclic codes over the ring $\mathfrak{R}$ of length n then,

$$\begin{aligned} J(\zeta) &= ((\nu)\zeta_{n-1}, \zeta_0, \dots, \zeta_{n-2}) \\ &= ((1+\nu)\dot{a}_{n-1} - (1-\nu)\dot{b}_{n-1}, (1+\nu)\dot{a}_0 + (1-\nu)\dot{b}_0, \dots, (1+\nu)\dot{a}_{n-2} + (1-\nu)\dot{b}_{n-2}) \\ &= (1+\nu)Y(\dot{a}) + (1-\nu)\Lambda(\dot{b}) \end{aligned}$$

which is an element of the linear code K . Therefore, K_1 is a cyclic code and K_2 is a negacyclic code over Z_3 of length n .

Conversely For any $\zeta = (\zeta_0, \zeta_1, \dots, \zeta_{n-1}) \in K$, where $\zeta_i = (1+\nu)\dot{a}_i + (1-\nu)\dot{b}_i$ and $\dot{a}_i, \dot{b}_i \in$

Z_3 for $i = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$. If K_1 is a cyclic code and K_2 is a negacyclic code over Z_3 of length n , then $\Upsilon(\dot{a}) \in K_1$ and $(\Lambda(\dot{b})) \in K_2$. Hence, we have $(1+\nu)\Upsilon(\dot{a}) + (1-\nu)\Lambda(\dot{b}) \in K$ where $J(\zeta) = (1+\nu)\Upsilon(\dot{a}) + (1-\nu)\Lambda(\dot{b})$, which implies that $J(\zeta)$ is in K . Therefore, K is a (ν) -constacyclic codes over the ring $\mathfrak{R}$ of length n .

The following lemma is Similar to.

Lemma 3.4 [11] Let K be a (ν) -constacyclic codes over the ring $\mathfrak{R}$ of length n . Then

$$K = \langle (1+\nu)g_1(x), (1-\nu)g_2(x) \rangle = \langle (1+\nu)g_1(x) + (1-\nu)g_2(x) \rangle$$

with $|K| = 3^{2n - \deg(g_1(x)) - \deg(g_2(x))}$, where $g_1, g_2(x)$ are generator polynomials of K_1 and K_2 respectively.

Moreover, $K^\perp = (1+\nu)K_1^\perp \oplus (1-\nu)K_2^\perp$ is also ν -constacyclic codes over the ring $\mathfrak{R}$ of length n and $K^\perp = \langle (1+\nu)g_1^{\hat{a}}(x), (1-\nu)g_2^{\hat{a}}(x) \rangle = \langle (1+\nu)g_1^{\hat{a}}(x) + (1-\nu)g_2^{\hat{a}}(x) \rangle$,

with $|K^\perp| = 3^{\deg(g_1(x)) + \deg(g_2(x))}$ where $g_i^{\hat{a}}(x)$ are the reciprocal polynomial of $\frac{x^n+1}{g_1(x)}$ and $\frac{x^n-1}{g_2(x)}$

for $i = 1, 2$ respectively.

Lemma 3.5 [4] If K is a cyclic or negacyclic code over the ring Z_3 with generator polynomial $g(x)$. Then, K contains its dual code if and only if $x^n - t \equiv 0 \pmod{g(x)g^{\hat{a}}(x)}$, where $t = \pm 1$

Theorem 3.6 If $K = \langle (1+\nu)g_1(x), (1-\nu)g_2(x) \rangle$ is a (ν) -constacyclic codes over the ring $\mathfrak{R}$ of length n . Then $K^\perp \subseteq K$ if and only if $x^n - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{g_1(x)g_1^{\hat{a}}(x)}$ for K_1 and $x^n + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{g_2(x)g_2^{\hat{a}}(x)}$ for K_2 .

Proof. Let $K = \langle g(x) \rangle = \langle (1+\nu)g_1(x) + (1-\nu)g_2(x) \rangle$ be a (ν) -constacyclic codes over the ring $\mathfrak{R}$ of length n . Then $K = (1+\nu)K_1 \oplus (1-\nu)K_2$ where $g_i(x)$ are generator polynomial of K_1 and K_2 for $i = 1, 2$ respectively.

First we consider $x^n - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{g_1(x)g_1^{\hat{a}}(x)}$ for K_1 and $x^n + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{g_2(x)g_2^{\hat{a}}(x)}$ for K_2 respectively, then by above lemma, we have

$$K_1^\perp \subseteq K_1 \text{ and } K_2^\perp \subseteq K_2$$

and therefore $(1+\nu)K_1^\perp \subseteq (1+\nu)K_1$ and $(1-\nu)K_2^\perp \subseteq (1-\nu)K_2$ which implies that

$$(1+\nu)K_1^\perp \oplus (1-\nu)K_2^\perp \subseteq (1+\nu)K_1 \oplus (1-\nu)K_2$$

Thus, we have $\langle (1+\nu)g_1^{\hat{a}}(x) + (1-\nu)g_2^{\hat{a}}(x) \rangle \subseteq \langle (1+\nu)g_1(x) + (1-\nu)g_2(x) \rangle$

and hence, $K^\perp \subseteq K$.

Conversely let us consider $K^\perp \subseteq K$, then

$$(1+\nu)K_1^\perp \oplus (1-\nu)K_2^\perp \subseteq (1+\nu)K_1 \oplus (1-\nu)K_2,$$

which implies that

$$(1+\nu)K_1^\perp \subseteq (1+\nu)K_1 \text{ and } (1-\nu)K_2^\perp \subseteq (1-\nu)K_2,$$

hence

$$K_1^\perp \subseteq K_1 \text{ and } K_2^\perp \subseteq K_2.$$

therefore we have

$$x^n - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{(g_1(x)g_1^*(x))} \text{ for } K_1 \text{ and } x^n + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{(g_2(x)g_2^*(x))} \text{ for } 2.$$

By the help above Theorem, we have the following corollary.

Corollary 3.7 Let $K = (1+\nu)K_1 \oplus (1-\nu)K_2$ be a (ν) -constacyclic codes over the ring $\mathfrak{R}$ of length n where K_1 and K_2 are linear code over Z_3 of length n . Then $K^\perp \subseteq K$ if and only if $K_1^\perp \subseteq K_1$ and $K_2^\perp \subseteq K_2$.

Lemma 3.8 [4](CSS Construction) Let K be a linear code over the ring Z_3 having parameters $[n, k, d]$. Then a quantum code having parameters $[n, 2k - n, \geq d]_3$ can be obtained if $K^\perp \subseteq K$.

The following theorem defines the construction of quantum codes by the use of corollary 3.7 and Lemma 3.8.

Theorem 3.9 If $K = (1+\nu)K_1 \oplus (1-\nu)K_2 = \langle (1+\nu)g_1(x) + (1-\nu)g_2(x) \rangle$ is a (ν) -constacyclic codes over the ring $\mathfrak{R}$ of length n where, $g_i(x)$ are the generator polynomials of K_1 and K_2 for $i = 1, 2$ respectively. If $K_1^\perp \subseteq K_1$ and $K_2^\perp \subseteq K_2$ then $K^\perp \subseteq K$ and there exists a quantum code having parameters $[2n, 2k - 2n, \geq d_L]_3$ where k is the dimension of linear code $\varphi(K)$ and d_L is minimum Lee distance of linear code K .

Examples

In this section some examples are provided to illustrate the main result. Here, the quantum codes through (ν) -constacyclic codes over the ring $\mathfrak{R} = Z_3 + \nu Z_3$ where $\nu^2 = 1$ are obtain.

Example 4.1 In $Z_3(t)$, $t^9 - 1 = (t+2)^9$ and $t^9 + 1 = (t+1)(t^8 - t^7 + t^6 - t^5 + t^4 - t^3 + t^2 - t + 1)$. Now, let K be a (ν) -constacyclic codes over the ring $\mathfrak{R} = Z_3 + \nu Z_3$ where $\nu^2 = 1$ of length 9. Let $g_1(t) = t^2 + t + 1$ and $g_2(t) = t + 1$, $g(t) = (1+\nu)(t^2 + t + 1) + (1-\nu)(t + 1)$ be the generator polynomial of K . Since $g_1(t)g_1^*(t) | t^9 - 1$ and $g_2(t)g_2^*(t) | t^9 + 1$, then by the use of Theorem 3.6, we get $K^\perp \subseteq K$. Further $\varphi(K)$ is a linear code over Z_3 having parameters $[18, 15, 2]$. Then, by the application of Theorem 3.9, we obtain the quantum codes having parameters $[18, 12, \geq 2]_3$.

Example 4.2 In $Z_3(t)$, $t^{12} - 1 = (t+1)^3(t+2)^3(t^2+1)^3$ and $t^{12} + 1 = (t^2 + 2t + 2)^3(t^2 + t + 2)^3$. Now, let K be a (ν) -constacyclic codes over the ring $\mathfrak{R} = Z_3 + \nu Z_3$ where $\nu^2 = 1$ of length 12. Let $g_1(t) = t + 1$ and $g_2(t) = t^2 + 2t + 2$, $g(t) = (1+\nu)(t + 1) + (1-\nu)(t^2 + 2t + 2)$ be the generator polynomial of K . Since $g_1(t)g_1^*(t) | t^{12} - 1$ and $g_2(t)g_2^*(t) | t^{12} + 1$, then by the use of Theorem 3.6, we get $K^\perp \subseteq K$. Further $\varphi(K)$ is a linear code over Z_3 having parameters $[24, 21, 2]$. Then, by the application of Theorem 3.9, we obtain the quantum codes having parameters $[24, 18, \geq 2]_3$.

Table: Some examples of Quantum codes with different parameter.

n	Generator Polynomials	$\varphi()$	$[n \ k \ d]$
4	$_1(\dagger) = \dagger_2 + 1$ and $_2(\dagger) = \dagger + 2$	[8,5,3]	[8,2, ≥ 3]
5	$_1(\dagger) = \dagger + 2$ and $_2(\dagger) = \dagger + 1$	[10,8,2]	[10,6, ≥ 2]
10	$_1(\dagger) = \dagger + 2$ and $_2(\dagger) = \dagger^2 + 1$	[20,17,3]	[20,14, ≥ 3]
13	$_1(\dagger) = \dagger^3 + 2\dagger + 2$ and $_2(\dagger) = \dagger + 1$	[26,22,4]	[26,18, ≥ 4]
15	$_1(\dagger) = \dagger^2 + \dagger + 1$ and $_2(\dagger) = \dagger^3 + 1$	[30,25,4]	[30,20, ≥ 4]
20	$_1(\dagger) = \dagger^2 + 1$ and $_2(\dagger) = \dagger^2 + \dagger + 2$	[40,37,3]	[40,34, ≥ 3]
21	$_1(\dagger) = \dagger^2 + \dagger + 1$ and $_2(\dagger) = \dagger^3 + 1$	[42,37,4]	[40,32, ≥ 4]
22	$_1(\dagger) = \dagger + 2$ and $_2(\dagger) = \dagger^2 + 1$	[44,41,3]	[44,38, ≥ 3]

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